

soil, bundled in nylon net, and buried about 5 cm deep in the root zone. Sclerotia survival was recorded at 1 1/2, 2, and 2 1/2 mo after burial. After the specified burial period, sclerotia were retrieved from the bundles, sterilized in mercuric chloride, and put in petri dishes previously layered with potato dextrose agar fortified with streptomycin sulfate for recording germination.

The figure shows that although survival rate of the sclerotia did not vary markedly in the root zones of rice and weeds, it declined significantly in the root zone of dhaincha. In all the cases, survival rate was less after 2 1/2 mo than after 1 1/2 mo. It appears that the environment of dhaincha root reduces survival of the sclerotia of *R. solani*. However, dhaincha leaves became severely infected when artificially inoculated with the fungus. □

Percent survival of *R. solani* sclerotia in the root zone of different plants at different periods.

Influence of bacterial leaf streak (BLS) on bacterial blight (BB) of rice

A. Premalatha Dath and S. Devadath, Division of Plant Pathology, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack 753006, Orissa, India

BB (caused by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*) and BLS (caused by *X. campestris* pv. *oryzicola*) are the most important bacterial diseases of rice in India. In the rainy months of Jul-Sep, both diseases affect rice over a substantial area. Rainy weather favors disease dissemination and infection. The bacterial

ooze from the leaves under high humidity is spread by wind-driven rains and by leaf contact.

We studied the interaction of the diseases on leaves of AC360, a cultivar highly susceptible to both diseases.

Leaves were inoculated with BLS by rubbing, then 2 d later were inoculated with BB by clipping. Disease development was assessed 5-7 d later. The progressive end of the BB lesion failed to develop water-soaking and it progressed slowly with orange discoloration, indicating almost a masking effect of BLS on BB development.

When leaves were first inoculated with

BB and inoculated with BLS 4 d later, disease assessment at 3 d showed BLS lesions developed more slowly than when leaves were inoculated first with BLS. Lesions turned brown and produced less bacterial ooze than did the rapidly elongating water-soaked lesions with abundant bacterial ooze that developed far from the BB lesion and also on leaves with only BLS infection. In screening rices for resistance to BB and BLS, caution needs to be exercised in rating their reaction if the plants are infected with both pathogens. □

Purification and serology of rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV)

H. Hibino and P. Q. Cabauatan, Plant Pathology Department, IRRI

We used the procedure followed for rice waika virus (RWV) in Japan to purify RTSV. RTSV-infected TNI plants (without roots) were homogenized in 0.01 M ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA), pH 8.0. The sap was clarified by heating at 40°C for 1 h and the virus was precipitated with 7% polyethylene

glycol 6,000, 0.2 M sodium chloride, and 1% triton X-100.

The resuspended virus was treated with 20% carbon tetrachloride and subjected to different centrifugation (40,000 rpm for 40 min, then 10,000 rpm for 10 min, at 4°C in a Beckman RT-65 rotor). Supernatant was layered on 10-50% linear sucrose density gradient (prepared in 0.01 M phosphate buffer [PB], pH 7.4), and centrifuged at 25,000 rpm for 180 min at 4°C in a Beckman SW 27 rotor.

The light scattering band (virus zone,

about 3 cm from the meniscus) was collected, diluted with 0.01 M EDTA (pH 8.0), and centrifuged at 40,000 rpm for 40 min. The virus was resuspended in 0.01 M PB (pH 7.4) and centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 10 min. The resulting supernatant contained isometric particles about 30 nm in diameter very similar to RWV (Fig. 1). Purified preparations had maximum ultraviolet (UV)-light absorption at 259-260 nm and minimum at 239-240 nm. The UV absorption ratio at 260 nm and 280 nm (A_{260}/A_{280}) for purified virus ranged from 1.52 to 1.74.